

Densities, viscosities, viscosity deviations and excess thermodynamic properties of ternary liquid mixtures of ethylenediamine/propylenediamine + 1,4-dioxane + (benzene or + toluene or + carbon tetrachloride) and their constituent binaries at 303.15 K

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Manuscript received 14 November 2007, revised 22 May 2008, accepted 26 May 2008

Abstract : Densities and viscosities of ternary liquid mixtures of ethylenediamine and propylenediamine with 1,4-dioxane, as the second common component, and benzene/toluene/carbon tetrachloride as the third component and their constituent binaries have been measured at 303.15 K. The viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) and thermodynamic excess properties (V^E and $\Delta G^{#E}$) have been determined and fitted to Cibulka's equation. The experimental values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{#E}$ have been found to be in close agreement with the theoretical values predicted by Cibulka's equation. The nature and strength of molecular interactions between the mixing components of the ternary liquid mixtures are also discussed.

Keywords : Viscosities, viscosity deviations, thermodynamic excess properties, ternary mixtures.

Introduction

Oswal and Rao¹ have determined viscosities of the binary liquid mixtures of some tertiary amines with cyclohexane and benzene and computed the values of the thermodynamic excess properties and characteristic parameter d in Nissan-Grunberg equation². Fernandez *et al.*³ determined excess molar enthalpy (H^E) of binary mixtures of benzene with *n*-alkylamines at 303.15 K. Weng⁴ has reported studies on the measurements of densities and viscosities for the binary mixtures of butylamine with 1-butanol, 1-pentanol, 1-hexanol, 1-heptanol and 1-octanol at 303.15 K, 313.15 K and 323.15 K over the entire composition range. Subha *et al.*⁵ have measured densities and viscosities of ethoxy ethanol with *n*-butylamine, *sec*-butylamine, *tert*-butylamine, *n*-hexylamine, *n*-octylamine and cyclohexylamine at 308.15 K. From the experimental data the excess molar volume (V^E), deviation in viscosity ($\Delta\eta$) and excess Gibbs free energies of the activation of viscous flow ($\Delta G^{#E}$) have been computed and presented as function of composition. However, such studies with regard to ternary mixtures involving aliphatic amines are rare. Dominguez and co-workers^{6,7} have carried out studies on the measurement

of densities and viscosities of ternary mixtures of 1-butanol + 1-chlorobutane + 1-butylamine; 2-methyl-1-propanol + 1-chlorobutane + 1-butylamine at 298.15 K; and 2-butanol + *n*-hexane + 1-butylamine at 298.15 K and 313.15 K. From the density and viscosity data, the values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{#E}$ have been determined and fitted to Cibulka⁸ equation.

From the above survey of literature, it is evident that studies relating to the measurement, correlation and prediction of viscosities as well as the thermodynamic excess properties in respect of ternary mixtures of diamines with non-polar solvents are still lacking. With this aim in view, the title study has been undertaken.

Results and discussion

The viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) and the thermodynamic excess properties viz. the excess molar volumes (V^E) and the excess Gibbs free energies of activation of viscous flow ($\Delta G^{#E}$) of the ternary liquid mixtures and their constituent binaries were determined as per details reported in our earlier publications^{9,10}.

The experimental values of densities (ρ), viscosities

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(η), viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$), excess molar volumes (V^E) and the excess Gibbs free energies of activation of viscous flow ($\Delta G^{\#E}$) at 303.15 K of the ternary mixtures involving ethylenediamine and propylenediamine as the first component, 1,4-dioxane as the second (common) component and benzene/toluene/carbon tetrachloride as the third component are presented in Table 1. The values of ρ , η , $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ in respect of the constituent binaries of these ternary mixtures are presented in Table 2.

Correlation of experimental values of viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) and excess thermodynamic properties (V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$) of ternary liquid mixtures with the theoretical values :

The experimentally determined values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ of constituent binaries are fitted to Redlich-Kister's equation¹¹ (eq. 1)

$$Y_{ij}^E = x_i x_j \sum_{p=0}^P A_p (x_i - x_j)^p \quad (1)$$

Table 1. Densities (ρ), viscosities (η), viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) and thermodynamic excess properties (V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$) of ternary liquid mixtures at 303.15 K

x_1	x_2	x_3	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	η (mPa s)	$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	V (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)
Ethylenediamine (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) + benzene (3)								
0.0664	0.0513	0.8823	0.8692	0.5740	-0.0611	89.079	0.5210	-149.36
0.0640	0.8890	0.0470	0.8843	0.6670	-0.3736	97.080	11.7129	-770.61
0.1256	0.7808	0.0936	0.8908	0.6400	-0.3908	93.911	9.5575	-879.39
0.1295	0.1008	0.7698	0.8334	0.5821	-0.1210	92.147	5.2399	-182.00
0.1290	0.2000	0.6710	0.8800	0.6251	-0.1258	88.394	1.8684	-250.00
0.1278	0.3971	0.4751	0.8900	0.6740	-0.1719	89.640	3.8502	-310.48
0.2498	0.1936	0.5566	0.8915	0.6649	-0.1669	84.742	1.0004	-345.44
0.2445	0.6645	0.0911	0.8923	0.6580	-0.3991	90.059	8.0104	-898.28
0.2457	0.5721	0.1822	0.8903	0.6760	-0.3369	89.190	6.8206	-720.70
0.3614	0.2805	0.3581	0.8990	0.6741	-0.2776	82.766	1.9563	-639.00
0.3585	0.4643	0.1772	0.8978	0.6670	-0.3720	84.982	4.8173	-863.15
0.4679	0.2719	0.2602	0.9030	0.7410	-0.2806	80.180	1.8136	-604.00
0.4660	0.3614	0.1725	0.9059	0.7048	-0.3589	80.940	2.8858	-833.09
0.5716	0.0889	0.3395	0.8846	0.7820	-0.2228	77.663	0.9997	-414.31
0.6644	0.1715	0.1641	0.9089	0.8480	-0.2615	74.661	0.4753	-548.01
0.6615	0.2565	0.0820	0.9068	0.8711	-0.2777	75.829	1.9051	-561.23
0.7532	0.1667	0.0801	0.9075	0.9720	-0.1969	72.961	0.8216	-368.30
0.8401	0.0817	0.0782	0.9043	1.0730	-0.1151	70.548	0.1006	-190.90
0.8824	0.0404	0.0772	0.9023	1.1440	-0.0534	69.403	0.2215	-64.47
0.9223	0.0399	0.0378	0.9013	1.2680	-0.0431	68.677	0.2135	-63.24
Ethylenediamine (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) + toluene (3)								
0.0885	0.0590	0.8525	0.8580	0.5430	-0.0762	103.807	1.2467	-152.33
0.0740	0.8860	0.0400	0.8766	0.6180	-0.4264	98.333	12.5044	-948.79
0.1459	0.7762	0.0780	0.8820	0.6270	-0.4126	95.631	10.3916	-924.69
0.1681	0.1121	0.7198	0.8714	0.6180	-0.0878	99.039	0.8000	-90.93
0.1646	0.2185	0.6168	0.8664	0.6248	-0.1345	99.234	3.0923	-182.69
0.1578	0.4198	0.4225	0.8600	0.6490	-0.2115	99.304	7.0818	-323.67
0.3064	0.2028	0.4908	0.8368	0.6773	-0.1782	97.402	6.6374	-154.00
0.2788	0.6470	0.0743	0.8360	0.6760	-0.3934	96.422	13.8359	-694.66
0.4061	0.4495	0.1444	0.8250	0.7460	-0.3130	93.718	12.1390	-408.98
0.5268	0.2623	0.2109	0.8300	0.8226	-0.2266	89.403	8.7706	-179.00

Table-1 (contd.)

0.5178	0.3440	0.1382	0.8280	0.8170	-0.2687	89.569	10.2851	-281.22
0.6407	0.0852	0.2741	0.8390	0.8484	-0.1914	84.945	2.3061	-133.00
0.7150	0.1579	0.1271	0.8490	0.9630	-0.1699	80.795	5.5648	-104.38
0.7039	0.2335	0.0626	0.8460	0.9328	-0.2318	81.142	7.0471	-254.00
0.7902	0.1496	0.0602	0.8626	1.0330	-0.1509	76.767	4.3947	-123.77
0.8696	0.0724	0.0580	0.8802	1.1121	-0.0896	72.695	1.9077	-63.45
0.9075	0.0355	0.0570	0.8878	1.1480	-0.0622	70.873	0.8405	-41.71
0.9373	0.0346	0.0281	0.9044	1.2601	-0.0570	68.520	5.0000	-146.00
Ethylenediamine (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) + carbon tetrachloride (3)								
0.0710	0.0549	0.8741	1.4480	0.8526	-0.0200	99.143	4.4052	-288.00
0.0643	0.8920	0.0437	1.0024	0.8988	-0.1551	88.963	3.2998	-294.79
0.1265	0.7861	0.0874	1.0364	0.8450	-0.2123	87.142	2.2000	-478.49
0.1373	0.1069	0.7558	1.3400	0.8210	-0.0915	99.946	7.8049	-255.01
0.1357	0.2104	0.6539	1.3197	0.7670	-0.1676	96.443	5.4000	-251.00
0.1324	0.4116	0.4560	1.2621	0.7480	-0.2294	90.613	1.7000	-579.96
0.2605	0.2019	0.5376	1.0740	0.8321	-0.1542	108.137	20.8017	-180.00
0.2461	0.6689	0.0851	1.0298	0.7340	-0.3490	84.308	1.7000	-896.90
0.2490	0.5798	0.1713	1.0584	0.7150	-0.3496	87.306	3.7990	-849.54
0.3713	0.2882	0.3405	0.9860	0.7070	-0.3459	101.505	18.5017	-425.98
0.3631	0.4703	0.1665	0.9750	0.6920	-0.3974	91.150	9.9251	-801.77
0.4768	0.2772	0.2460	0.9140	0.7380	-0.3578	99.474	19.5627	-376.91
0.4719	0.3660	0.1621	0.9110	0.7320	-0.3812	93.901	14.8242	-567.90
0.5865	0.0912	0.3223	0.8740	0.7037	-0.3984	106.248	27.6162	-289.07
0.6724	0.1736	0.1540	0.8690	0.8567	-0.3004	91.364	16.2627	-206.56
0.6654	0.2580	0.0766	0.8640	0.8760	-0.2966	86.233	11.8542	-319.57
0.7576	0.1676	0.0747	0.8660	0.9550	-0.2373	82.898	10.3349	-184.08
0.8449	0.0822	0.0729	0.8740	1.0439	-0.1671	79.216	8.3562	-60.00
0.8873	0.0406	0.0721	0.8950	1.0840	-0.1361	75.971	5.9423	-63.03
0.9249	0.0400	0.0351	0.9098	1.2800	-0.1231	70.906	2.0153	-60.05
Propylenediamine (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) + benzene (3)								
0.0521	0.0521	0.8958	0.8570	0.5742	-0.0552	91.513	1.6000	-104.82
0.0503	0.9021	0.0477	0.9592	0.9700	-0.0712	90.634	4.0000	-42.43
0.0998	0.8038	0.0964	0.9653	0.9555	-0.0760	88.829	2.0000	-89.21
0.1030	0.1038	0.7932	0.8650	0.5992	-0.0946	91.027	1.4960	-191.36
0.1026	0.2061	0.6913	0.8850	0.6002	-0.1430	90.127	0.9917	-360.29
0.1016	0.4090	0.4894	0.9040	0.6124	-0.2286	90.482	2.1291	-592.99
0.2052	0.2052	0.5897	0.8280	0.6754	-0.1464	95.837	7.0551	-120.00
0.2005	0.7031	0.0964	0.8320	0.7200	-0.3401	101.374	14.5138	-531.25
0.2016	0.6056	0.1928	0.8390	0.7189	-0.2947	99.361	12.1267	-445.99
0.3046	0.3055	0.3900	0.7770	0.7347	-0.2124	102.909	14.8707	-80.00
0.3019	0.5052	0.1928	0.7740	0.7585	-0.2835	105.882	18.6257	-211.00
0.4044	0.3044	0.2912	0.7490	0.7651	-0.2582	106.201	18.5232	-102.00
0.4026	0.4044	0.1930	0.7440	0.7940	-0.2766	108.268	20.9718	-102.00
0.5075	0.1022	0.3903	0.7480	0.7926	-0.2119	103.091	14.9976	-7.00
0.6049	0.2019	0.1932	0.7420	0.8953	-0.2326	104.746	17.3865	-6.20
0.6017	0.3017	0.0965	0.7370	0.9124	-0.2615	106.817	19.8423	-47.00

Table-1 (contd.)

0.7023	0.2010	0.0966	0.7620	0.9996	-0.2028	101.466	14.4595	-7.80
0.8024	0.1010	0.0966	0.8280	1.1290	-0.1019	91.699	4.6528	-18.56
0.8529	0.0505	0.0966	0.8206	1.2252	-0.0201	91.661	4.6000	-42.00
0.9018	0.0504	0.0478	0.8500	1.3510	-0.0199	88.265	1.3772	-40.00
Propylenediamine (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) + toluene (3)								
0.0608	0.0608	0.8784	0.8601	0.5631	-0.0411	105.569	0.7324	-40.00
0.0506	0.9084	0.0410	0.9936	1.0088	-0.0340	88.132	0.8331	-33.00
0.1014	0.8166	0.0820	0.9679	0.9483	-0.0873	89.913	1.7399	-120.00
0.1178	0.1189	0.7633	0.8590	0.5391	-0.1420	104.234	1.7898	-356.29
0.1152	0.2315	0.6533	0.8800	0.6170	-0.1214	101.287	1.1468	-219.95
0.1102	0.4435	0.4464	0.8770	0.5920	-0.2541	100.772	4.9575	-585.51
0.2262	0.2262	0.5475	0.8430	0.6532	-0.1723	103.375	5.4253	-219.68
0.2037	0.7143	0.0820	0.8360	0.7080	-0.3566	102.384	14.1793	-591.68
0.2079	0.6247	0.1674	0.8400	0.7245	-0.2963	102.236	12.2420	-436.47
0.3246	0.3255	0.3499	0.8140	0.7687	-0.1891	104.401	10.5494	-85.01
0.3114	0.5212	0.1674	0.8250	0.7140	-0.3362	102.341	12.3152	-534.05
0.4241	0.3192	0.2567	0.8170	0.7930	-0.2421	101.855	9.9248	-242.48
0.4153	0.4171	0.1676	0.8160	0.7910	-0.2886	101.691	11.6287	-355.37
0.5408	0.1089	0.3502	0.8173	0.8334	-0.1855	100.272	2.3061	-114.00
0.6240	0.2083	0.1677	0.8153	0.9536	-0.1853	98.200	8.0717	-100.00
0.6113	0.3065	0.0822	0.8212	0.9430	-0.2373	97.291	8.9570	-247.21
0.7135	0.2042	0.0822	0.8270	1.0669	-0.1423	94.870	6.5136	-61.00
0.8152	0.1026	0.0822	0.8417	1.1466	-0.0916	91.535	3.1381	-32.98
0.8665	0.0513	0.0822	0.8465	1.2640	-0.0112	90.172	1.7592	-31.02
0.9081	0.0507	0.0411	0.8544	1.3420	-0.0559	88.450	0.8940	-30.00
Propylenediamine (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) + carbon tetrachloride (3)								
0.0558	0.0558	0.8884	1.4809	0.8133	-0.0571	98.389	2.0999	-95.00
0.0504	0.9052	0.0443	1.0260	1.0104	-0.0441	88.019	1.0965	-67.89
0.1005	0.8094	0.0900	0.9968	0.9551	-0.1036	92.907	5.4629	-91.00
0.1094	0.1104	0.7802	1.4240	0.8510	-0.0584	96.806	1.7000	-85.64
0.1081	0.2171	0.6748	1.3508	0.8600	-0.0722	96.937	3.0000	-85.32
0.1054	0.4244	0.4702	1.2534	0.8997	-0.0768	93.768	2.0992	-112.71
0.2145	0.2145	0.5710	1.1200	0.7783	-0.2070	109.493	16.6730	-125.00
0.2019	0.7080	0.0900	0.9531	0.8830	-0.2044	95.675	8.1994	-276.83
0.2044	0.6142	0.1814	1.0540	0.8870	-0.1811	92.198	3.6999	-335.04
0.3137	0.3146	0.3717	1.0400	0.8740	-0.1833	103.989	13.3482	-80.96
0.3062	0.5124	0.1814	1.0560	0.8800	-0.2171	90.672	2.1420	-459.42
0.4131	0.3109	0.2760	1.0150	0.9000	-0.2066	98.986	9.3751	-219.82
0.4083	0.4101	0.1816	1.0135	0.9060	-0.2200	93.078	4.5152	-382.46
0.5227	0.1053	0.3721	0.9400	0.8655	-0.2512	111.981	21.2626	-48.00
0.6135	0.2048	0.1817	0.9120	1.0189	-0.1654	100.299	11.6718	-23.78
0.6060	0.3039	0.0902	0.9160	1.0200	-0.1824	93.419	5.7999	-223.09
0.7073	0.2025	0.0903	0.9084	1.1143	-0.1168	92.652	5.0000	-83.00
0.8081	0.1017	0.0903	0.8800	1.2240	-0.0357	94.040	6.3573	-129.00
0.8589	0.0508	0.0903	0.8760	1.2970	-0.0229	93.649	5.9589	-234.00
0.9050	0.0506	0.0445	0.8632	1.3569	-0.0219	90.814	3.6095	-125.00

Table 2. Densities (ρ), viscosities (η), viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) and thermodynamic excess properties (V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$) of constituent binary liquid mixtures at 303.15 K

x_1	x_2	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	η (mPa s)	$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	V (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)
Ethylenediamine (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2)							
0.0000	1.0000	1.0195	1.0500	0.0000	86.425	0.0000	0.00
0.1252	0.8748	0.9804	0.9063	-0.1699	86.298	2.2993	-351.96
0.2435	0.7565	0.9500	0.7660	-0.3350	85.566	3.8600	-775.89
0.3556	0.6444	0.9248	0.7659	-0.3586	84.504	4.9700	-787.39
0.4624	0.5376	0.9071	0.7262	-0.4207	82.854	5.3900	-951.88
0.5630	0.4370	0.8945	0.7612	-0.4068	80.875	5.3600	-875.96
0.6591	0.3409	0.8864	0.7849	-0.4032	78.572	4.9201	-854.06
0.7505	0.2495	0.8830	0.8479	-0.3594	75.981	4.1000	-727.43
0.8378	0.1622	0.8840	0.9220	-0.3036	73.129	2.9400	-596.87
0.9204	0.0796	0.8940	1.1612	-0.0817	69.719	1.1303	-120.91
1.0000	0.0000	0.8964	1.2596	0.0000	67.046	0.0000	0.00
Ethylenediamine (1) + benzene (3)							
0.0000	1.0000	0.8650	0.5640	0.0000	90.301	0.0000	0.00
0.1300	0.8700	0.8594	0.6038	-0.0506	88.168	0.8901	-54.00
0.2517	0.7483	0.8501	0.6467	-0.0924	86.547	2.0999	-83.00
0.3658	0.6342	0.8455	0.6937	-0.1247	84.594	2.8000	-109.00
0.4734	0.5266	0.8456	0.7494	-0.1439	82.292	3.0000	-121.00
0.5738	0.4262	0.8468	0.8107	-0.1524	80.037	3.0801	-121.00
0.6689	0.3311	0.8513	0.8808	-0.1485	77.606	2.8600	-111.00
0.7587	0.2413	0.8570	0.9554	-0.1364	75.197	2.5398	-100.00
0.8437	0.1563	0.8673	1.0433	-0.1075	72.541	1.8606	-77.00
0.9236	0.0764	0.8811	1.1435	-0.0630	69.772	0.9491	-46.00
1.0000	0.0000	0.8964	1.2596	0.0000	67.046	0.0000	0.00
Ethylenediamine (1) + toluene (3)							
0.0000	1.0000	0.8582	0.5229	0.0000	107.364	0.0000	0.00
0.1719	0.8281	0.8550	0.5829	-0.0666	101.324	0.8900	-49.00
0.3190	0.6810	0.8501	0.6460	-0.1119	96.363	1.8600	-68.00
0.4451	0.5549	0.8498	0.7111	-0.1397	91.649	2.2300	-82.00
0.5549	0.4451	0.8520	0.7810	-0.1507	87.282	2.2900	-82.00
0.6517	0.3483	0.8555	0.8525	-0.1505	83.299	2.2100	-78.40
0.7371	0.2629	0.8604	0.9260	-0.1400	79.646	2.0000	-71.00
0.8139	0.1861	0.8678	1.0036	-0.1189	76.129	1.5800	-61.00
0.8823	0.1177	0.8752	1.0821	-0.0908	72.981	1.1900	-48.00
0.9440	0.0560	0.8839	1.1634	-0.0549	70.024	0.7200	-33.00
1.0000	0.0000	0.8964	1.2596	0.0000	67.046	0.0000	0.00
Ethylenediamine (1) + carbon tetrachloride (3)							
0.0000	1.0000	1.5775	0.8300	0.0000	97.509	0.0000	0.00
0.1390	0.8610	1.5078	0.8586	-0.0311	93.374	0.0996	-38.73
0.4926	0.5074	1.3014	0.9547	-0.0869	82.719	0.2160	-114.65
0.5925	0.4075	1.2339	0.9963	-0.0882	79.657	0.1970	-112.94
0.6858	0.3142	1.1662	1.0379	-0.0867	76.788	0.1707	-112.29
0.7722	0.2278	1.0988	1.0838	-0.0779	74.123	0.1380	-101.50

Table-2 (contd.)

0.8534	0.1466	1.0312	1.1352	-0.0614	71.607	0.0949	-80.49
0.9287	0.0713	0.9640	1.1867	-0.0423	69.275	0.0567	-60.19
1.0000	0.0000	0.8964	1.2596	0.0000	67.046	0.0000	0.00
Propylenediamine (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2)							
0.0000	1.0000	1.0195	1.0500	0.0000	86.425	0.0000	0.00
0.0995	0.9005	0.9928	0.8670	-0.2113	87.345	0.8900	-516.89
0.1997	0.8003	0.9701	0.6339	-0.4728	87.946	1.4600	-1350.22
0.2993	0.7007	0.9478	0.5860	-0.5490	88.547	2.0300	-1592.08
0.3991	0.6009	0.9279	0.5342	-0.6291	88.946	2.3990	-1875.10
0.4987	0.5013	0.9111	0.5824	-0.6092	89.058	2.4800	-1715.20
0.5991	0.4009	0.8970	0.6527	-0.5674	88.889	2.2800	-1494.24
0.6993	0.3007	0.8830	0.7705	-0.4781	88.710	2.0700	-1142.49
0.7997	0.2003	0.8712	0.9172	-0.3599	88.301	1.6300	-776.35
0.8995	0.1005	0.8631	1.1055	-0.2000	87.511	0.8100	-389.46
1.0000	0.0000	0.8547	1.3340	0.0000	86.732	0.0000	0.00
Propylenediamine (1) + benzene (3)							
0.0000	1.0000	0.8650	0.5640	0.0000	90.301	0.0000	0.00
0.1034	0.8966	0.8540	0.4654	-0.1782	90.981	1.0492	-679.24
0.2068	0.7932	0.8432	0.4140	-0.3092	91.663	2.1000	-1169.23
0.3087	0.6913	0.8331	0.3857	-0.4160	92.279	3.0800	-1541.55
0.4098	0.5902	0.8269	0.3981	-0.4814	92.488	3.6500	-1665.17
0.5097	0.4903	0.8232	0.4348	-0.5217	92.422	3.9400	-1651.34
0.6097	0.3903	0.8241	0.5155	-0.5180	91.835	3.7101	-1445.10
0.7085	0.2915	0.8276	0.6542	-0.4553	90.973	3.2001	-1072.67
0.8066	0.1934	0.8326	0.8395	-0.3456	89.962	2.5400	-675.13
0.9034	0.0966	0.8419	1.1339	-0.1257	88.507	1.4300	-158.78
1.0000	0.0000	0.8547	1.3340	0.0000	86.732	0.0000	0.00
Propylenediamine (1) + toluene (3)							
0.0000	1.0000	0.8582	0.5229	0.0000	107.364	0.0000	0.00
0.1207	0.8793	0.8536	0.5714	-0.0494	105.394	0.5200	-43.00
0.2367	0.7633	0.8494	0.6283	-0.0866	103.460	0.9795	-62.00
0.3467	0.6533	0.8460	0.6886	-0.1155	101.531	1.3200	-79.00
0.4520	0.5480	0.8441	0.7545	-0.1350	99.518	1.4791	-91.00
0.5528	0.4472	0.8426	0.8293	-0.1420	97.538	1.5791	-87.00
0.6498	0.3502	0.8431	0.9109	-0.1391	95.408	1.4500	-83.00
0.7431	0.2569	0.8442	1.0013	-0.1244	93.297	1.2640	-71.00
0.8321	0.1679	0.8467	1.1007	-0.0971	91.120	0.9240	-54.00
0.9178	0.0822	0.8501	1.2103	-0.0570	88.944	0.5160	-32.00
1.0000	0.0000	0.8547	1.3340	0.0000	86.732	0.0000	0.00
Propylenediamine (1) + carbon tetrachloride (3)							
0.0000	1.0000	1.0195	1.0500	0.0000	86.425	0.0000	0.00
0.0995	0.9005	0.9928	0.8670	-0.2113	87.345	0.8900	-516.89
0.1997	0.8003	0.9701	0.6339	-0.4728	87.946	1.4600	-1350.22
0.2993	0.7007	0.9478	0.5860	-0.5490	88.547	2.0300	-1592.08
0.3991	0.6009	0.9279	0.5342	-0.6291	88.946	2.3990	-1875.10
0.4987	0.5013	0.9111	0.5824	-0.6092	89.058	2.4800	-1715.20

Table-2 (contd.)

0.5991	0.4009	0.8970	0.6527	-0.5674	88.889	2.2800	-1494.24
0.6993	0.3007	0.8830	0.7705	-0.4781	88.710	2.0700	-1142.49
0.7997	0.2003	0.8712	0.9172	-0.3599	88.301	1.6300	-776.35
0.8995	0.1005	0.8631	1.1055	-0.2000	87.511	0.8100	-389.46
1.0000	0.0000	0.8547	1.3340	0.0000	86.732	0.0000	0.00
1,4-Dioxane (2) + benzene (3)							
0.0000	1.0000	0.8650	0.5640	0.0000	90.301	0.0000	0.00
0.1042	0.8958	0.8700	0.5890	-0.0256	90.979	1.0826	-23.51
0.2068	0.7932	0.8770	0.6180	-0.0465	91.423	1.9239	-39.48
0.3093	0.6907	0.8820	0.6500	-0.0643	92.067	2.9651	-43.78
0.4108	0.5892	0.8950	0.6870	-0.0766	91.864	3.1553	-57.58
0.5110	0.4890	0.9080	0.7290	-0.0833	91.652	3.3320	-59.71
0.6104	0.3896	0.9250	0.7780	-0.0827	91.042	3.1074	-57.28
0.7093	0.2907	0.9450	0.8340	-0.0747	90.162	2.6105	-50.57
0.8073	0.1927	0.9680	0.8950	-0.0613	89.032	1.8604	-47.11
0.9036	0.0964	0.9910	0.9670	-0.0361	87.937	1.1390	-23.47
1.0000	0.0000	1.0195	1.0500	0.0000	86.425	0.0000	0.00
1,4-Dioxane (2) + toluene (3)							
0.0000	1.0000	0.8582	0.5229	0.0000	107.364	0.0000	0.00
0.1216	0.8784	0.8610	0.5540	-0.0330	106.446	1.6279	-23.21
0.2367	0.7633	0.8680	0.5910	-0.0567	105.053	2.6452	-32.76
0.3473	0.6527	0.8770	0.6320	-0.0740	103.467	3.3748	-35.92
0.4530	0.5470	0.8880	0.6750	-0.0867	101.705	3.8268	-41.22
0.5541	0.4459	0.9020	0.7210	-0.0940	99.675	3.9134	-48.25
0.6504	0.3496	0.9170	0.7730	-0.0927	97.622	3.8763	-41.75
0.7438	0.2562	0.9370	0.8310	-0.0840	95.136	3.3467	-37.44
0.8327	0.1673	0.9620	0.8980	-0.0638	92.291	2.3634	-26.12
0.9180	0.0820	0.9900	0.9700	-0.0368	89.334	1.1920	-17.05
1.0000	0.0000	1.0195	1.0500	0.0000	86.425	0.0000	0.00
1,4-Dioxane (2) + carbon tetrachloride (3)							
0.0000	1.0000	1.5775	0.8300	0.0000	97.509	0.0000	0.00
0.1116	0.8884	1.5185	0.5692	-0.2854	96.467	0.1950	-1010.00
0.2198	0.7802	1.4597	0.4756	-0.4028	95.481	0.4085	-1520.00
0.3258	0.6742	1.4021	0.4304	-0.4713	94.440	0.5427	-1830.00
0.4295	0.5705	1.3455	0.3911	-0.5333	93.348	0.5996	-2130.00
0.5302	0.4698	1.2895	0.3956	-0.5511	92.272	0.6395	-2160.00
0.6286	0.3714	1.2346	0.4316	-0.5367	91.132	0.5903	-2000.00
0.7245	0.2755	1.1805	0.5078	-0.4816	89.972	0.4940	-1650.00
0.8187	0.1813	1.1261	0.6094	-0.4007	88.824	0.3896	-1250.00
0.9100	0.0900	1.0727	0.8140	-0.2162	87.654	0.2320	-580.00
1.0000	0.0000	1.0195	1.0500	0.0000	86.425	0.0000	0.00

where, V_{ij}^E is $\Delta\eta$ or V^E or $\Delta G^{#E}$; x_i denotes the mole fraction of component i of i, j mixtures with $x_j = 1 - x_i$; and A_p are adjustable parameters. Redlich-Kister equation is fitted to each set of the experimental values of $\Delta\eta$,

V^E and $\Delta G^{#E}$ for constituent binary mixtures to evaluate the values of parameters A_p by the least-squares method using a computer.

The viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$), the excess molar vol-

umes (V^E) and the excess Gibbs free energies of activation of viscous flow ($\Delta G^{\#E}$) for the ternary mixtures have been fitted to Cibulka's equation⁸ (eq. 2)

$$Y^E = Y_{\text{bin}}^E + x_1x_2x_3 [B_1 + B_2x_1 + B_3x_2] \quad (2)$$

where,

$$Y_{\text{bin}}^E = Y_{12}^E + Y_{13}^E + Y_{23}^E \quad (3)$$

Using the calculated values of parameters, A_p , the values of Y_{ij}^E are obtained applying eq. (1). Having thus obtained the values of Y_{bin}^E , the experimental values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ for ternary mixtures are fitted to Cibulka's equation (eq. 2) to obtain the values of coefficients B_1 , B_2 and B_3 by the method of least-squares. After the determination of coefficients B_1 , B_2 and B_3 , the theoretical (calculated) values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ for ternary mixtures

have been obtained from eq. (2).

The values of standard deviation, σ for $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ of the ternary mixtures and their constituent binaries have been obtained⁷ applying eq. (4).

$$\sigma(Y^E) = \left(\frac{\sum(Y_{\text{exp.}}^E - Y_{\text{calcd.}}^E)^2}{(n-p)} \right)^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

where Y^E is $\Delta\eta$ or V^E or $\Delta G^{\#E}$, n is the number of experimental data and p is the number of parameters.

The coefficients, A_p of the Redlich-Kister's equation, B_1 , B_2 and B_3 of Cibulka's equation and the corresponding standard deviation, σ , for $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ of the binary and ternary systems at 303.15 K are presented in Tables 3 and 4 respectively.

Table 3. Coefficients of Redlich-Kister's equation and the corresponding standard deviation, σ , for Y_{ij}^E of the constituent binaries at 303.15 K

Y_{ij}^E	A_0	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	A_5	A_6	A_7	σ
Ethylenediamine (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2)									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-1.6886	-0.3061	1.4522	0.8996	-13.6534	-1.4829	-	-	0.00135
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	21.7065	0.8098	2.1334	-34.7065	-16.0315	72.5918	-	-	0.0081
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-3773.74	-196.52	5927.93	-1448.57	-43761.15	16850.04	60802.34	-26200.56	4.0516
Ethylenediamine (1) + benzene (3)									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-0.5892	-0.1955	-0.0595	-0.3054	-0.1854	0.5312	-	-	0.0007
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	12.171	1.292	4.879	1.317	-18.398	20.653	-	-	0.0034
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-489.05	-14.52	121.36	-654.59	-573.99	1586.29	332.57	-1141.95	1.0382
Ethylenediamine (1) + toluene (3)									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	0.1164	-0.0159	-0.1162	-0.1926	0.1676	0.7080	-	-	0.00008
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	0.1164	0.8602	5.1011	8.4337	-34.4912	0.4420	-	-	0.0017
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	9.09	0.86	4.95	8.43	-34.49	0.44	44.55	-15.46	0.3525
Ethylenediamine (1) + carbon tetrachloride (3)									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-0.3484	-0.0612	-0.0828	-0.5056	-0.3025	1.8223	-	-	0.00010
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	0.862	-0.053	-1.370	1.250	8.003	-9.475	-	-	0.0010
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	0.86	-0.05	-1.37	1.25	8.00	-9.47	-10.80	13.56	0.3084
Propylenediamine (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2)									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-2.4779	0.8317	0.8106	-5.3083	-6.0546	21.1192	-	-	0.0001
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	9.849	-2.000	-1.199	-34.706	3.445	-38.247	-	-	0.0016
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-7034.60	4897.15	5334.24	-25936.62	-21455.11	91560.47	27916.15	-94844.87	4.5908
Propylenediamine (1) + benzene (3)									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-2.0791	-0.5700	0.1286	2.8983	-1.1309	-10.2247	-	-	0.0006
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	15.647	1.829	-6.750	-10.834	13.508	62.310	-	-	0.0021
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-6632.11	1538.66	2447.52	11426.34	-1029.34	-42693.03	2966.20	45797.78	1.6207
Propylenediamine (1) + toluene (3)									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-0.5590	-0.1493	-0.0104	-0.2394	-0.1360	0.7337	-	-	0.0002
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	6.160	1.331	0.021	-3.348	-3.330	11.500	-	-	0.0023
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-361.60	41.55	110.02	-823.18	-468.27	2566.12	287.27	-2144.81	1.2843

Propylenediamine (1) + carbon tetrachloride (3)									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	1.2205	1.1143	0.9560	-5.5467	-2.0426	22.3578	-	-	0.00017
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-14.940	-22.096	-31.051	-56.225	26.246	131.246	-	-	0.0023
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-14.94	-22.10	-31.05	-56.23	26.25	131.25	-126.66	-237.74	3.0547
1,4-Dioxane (1) + benzene (3)									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-0.3317	-0.0845	0.0393	0.1572	-0.2129	-0.7844	-	-	0.00004
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	13.071	1.166	7.764	-34.706	-54.872	138.355	-	-	0.0058
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-245.49	2.80	397.67	-526.77	-2116.75	1514.63	2277.43	-1162.22	1.5496
1,4-Dioxane (1) + toluene (3)									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-0.3635	-0.1358	-0.0409	-0.0800	-0.1050	0.6453	-	-	0.0004
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	15.587	2.624	4.949	12.246	-12.989	-53.742	-	-	0.0026
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-180.39	-85.04	137.01	258.17	-787.84	322.24	803.66	-843.49	1.9056
1,4-Dioxane (1) + carbon tetrachloride (3)									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-2.2098	-0.3056	0.2384	0.5555	-4.6876	-1.7618	-	-	0.0004
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	2.5230	0.4891	-0.4487	-5.7516	0.9504	19.6727	-	-	0.0044
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-8760.60	-134.19	5919.21	580.55	-24968.13	3782.70	24227.12	-17.33	1.8825

Table 4. Coefficients of Cibulka equation and the corresponding standard deviation, σ , for V^E of the ternary mixtures at 303.15 K

V^E	B_1	B_2	B_3	σ
Ethylenediamine (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) + benzene (3)				
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-3.1932	18.4883	-7.2267	0.0091
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	69.230	-784.245	651.002	0.0492
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-1362.12	18128.11	-24905.86	2.0416
Ethylenediamine (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) + toluene (3)				
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	8.8038	-19.9291	-37.4539	0.0013
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-248.389	548.523	1220.764	0.0333
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-9732.92	58141.74	-19602.12	2.8199
Ethylenediamine (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) + carbon tetrachloride (3)				
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-4.1258	3.6581	-12.3466	0.0071
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-272.360	139.600	199.380	0.0175
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	29689.36	-36230.98	-98597.02	3.7756
Propylenediamine (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) + benzene (3)				
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-1.2670	22.0114	11.5486	0.0015
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-399.419	1550.301	766.612	0.0269
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	16609.79	73141.68	5798.62	2.3426
Propylenediamine (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) + toluene (3)				
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	2.9941	-13.1390	-23.0407	0.0071
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-201.400	610.826	969.982	0.0219
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-39081.90	87208.24	78830.09	1.6610
Propylenediamine (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) + carbon tetrachloride (3)				
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-4.1258	3.6581	-12.3466	0.0071
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-272.360	139.600	199.380	0.0175
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	29689.36	-36230.98	-98597.02	3.7756

From the small values of σ ($\Delta\eta$)/ σ (V^E)/ σ ($\Delta G^{\#E}$) the experimental and theoretical values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ for the ternary liquid mixtures is fairly good.

The plots of densities (ρ) and viscosities (η) of the ternary liquid mixtures versus x_1 (the mole fraction of the first component, ethylenediamine/propylenediamine) are found to be non-linear (representative Fig. 1). This non-linear variation of ρ and η with the composition indicates^{12,13} the presence of molecular interactions between the mixing components of the ternary mixtures of ethylenediamine/propylenediamine with 1,4-dioxane and benzene/toluene/carbon tetrachloride.

According to Vogel and Wiess¹⁸, mixtures with strong interactions between different molecules result in positive viscosity deviations, whereas, for mixtures without strong interactions the viscosity deviations are negative. In this way, Meyer *et al.*¹⁹ state that excess Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow ($\Delta G^{\#E}$), like viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) can be used to detect molecular interactions. In the ternary mixtures under discussion the first component ethylenediamine/propylenediamine is an

Fig. 1. Variation of density (ρ) and viscosity (η) with mole fraction (x_1) of the first component in ternary liquid mixture of ethylenediamine + 1,4-dioxane + benzene at 303.15 K : (▲) density (ρ), (●) viscosity (η).

Viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) and thermodynamic excess properties (V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$) of ternary liquid systems vis-à-vis molecular interactions :

The values of $\Delta\eta$ and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ of ternary liquid mixtures of ethylenediamine and propylenediamine with 1,4-dioxane and benzene/toluene/carbon tetrachloride is negative over the entire range of composition range investigated. The negative values of $\Delta\eta$ and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ observed in the case of these ternary mixtures may be attributed to the presence of dispersion forces^{14,15}. This is also supported^{16,17} by the positive values of V^E .

The interpretation in regard to the negative values of $\Delta\eta$ and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ and positive values of V^E vis-à-vis molecular interactions in ternary mixtures is as below :

associated liquid due to the presence of intermolecular hydrogen bonding. On the other hand, the second and third components are non-associated liquids. The mixing of these components results in the breaking of hydrogen bonds in the associated molecules of the first component by the presence of two electronegative oxygen atoms in 1,4-dioxane, four-chlorine atoms in carbon tetrachloride and π -electrons in benzene and toluene. This makes the mixture to flow more easily as compared to the pure liquids. The negative values observed for $\Delta\eta$ and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ of the ternary mixtures under discussion point out the easier flow of the mixture compared with the behaviour of pure liquids. This is also in accordance with the conclusion of Fort and Moore²⁰ about the behaviour of systems containing an associated component.

According to Treszczanowicz *et al.*²¹ V^E is the result of contribution from several opposing effects. This may be divided into three types : physical, chemical and structural. Physical effect contributes a positive term to V^E . The chemical or specific intermolecular interactions result in a volume decrease and contribute negative values to V^E . The structural contributions are mostly negative and arise from interstitial accommodation and changes in the free volume. The actual volume change, therefore, depends on the relative strength of these effects. In the ternary mixtures of the present study, the first component (ethylenediamine/propylenediamine) is a polar liquid, the second component (1,4-dioxane) is a non-polar liquid and the third-component (benzene/toluene/carbon tetrachloride) is also a non-polar liquid. In these mixtures the physical effect predominates which arises due to dipole induced dipole interactions resulting in disruption in the favourable orientational order of ethylenediamine/propylenediamine and non-polar components. This gives rise to an increase in the volume of the mixture resulting in positive value of V^E .

The interactions in a ternary $i+j+k$ mixture are closely dependent²² on the interactions in the constituent $i+j$, $j+k$, and $i+k$ mixtures. It should therefore be possible to correlate the nature of interactions occurring in ternary mixtures with those of constituent binary mixtures. For all the constituent binaries corresponding to the ternary mixtures of ethylenediamine/propylenediamine with 1,4-dioxane and benzene/toluene/carbon tetrachloride the values of $\Delta\eta$ and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ are negative and those of V^E are positive over the entire range of composition investigated indicating that the interactions in these constituent binaries are of dispersive nature. Thus, the nature of molecular interactions in the ternary liquid mixtures of the title study is dependent on the interactions in their constituent binaries.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. Ethylenediamine (>99.5%), propylenediamine (>99.2%), 1,4-dioxane (>99.4%), benzene (>99.3%), toluene (>99.5%) and carbon tetrachloride (>99.3%) were obtained from Merck. The organic liquids were further purified according to the procedure described in literature^{23,24}.

Liquid mixtures of various compositions were prepared by mass in 25 cm³ flasks, using a Mettler analytical balance. The average uncertainty in the mole fraction

of the mixtures was estimated to be less than ± 0.0001 . Density and viscosity measurements were carried out using a thermostatically controlled, well-stirred water bath, where a constant temperature was measured with a digital thermometer with an uncertainty of ± 0.01 K.

Densities (ρ) of pure liquids and their mixtures were measured at 303.15 K with an Anton Parr digital vibrating tube densimeter (Model 60/602, Anton Parr, Austria). The densimeter was calibrated with degassed water and dehumidified air at atmospheric pressure. The uncertainty of the density measurements was estimated to be $\pm 1 \times 10^{-5}$ g cm⁻³.

The viscosities (η) of pure organic liquids and their binary and ternary mixtures were determined using an Ostwald viscometer, which was suspended in a thermostat maintained at (303.15 ± 0.01) K. The details of the procedure have been reported in an earlier publication⁹. The uncertainty of calculated absolute viscosities was $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ mPa s. The excess molar volumes were calculated from density data, and the uncertainties were estimated to be within $\pm 5 \times 10^{-3}$ cm³ mol⁻¹.

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